

**PRODUCTION OF FISH FEEDS BASED ON MODERN
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+99890-106-95-55<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18264073>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 13th January 2026Accepted: 14th January 2026Online: 15th January 2026**KEYWORDS***fish feeds, components, extrusion,
starch hydrolysis, elements,
energy sources.***ABSTRACT***The purpose of this study is to advance the application of biotechnological methods in feed production through microbiological research, and to address the challenges associated with producing high-protein, balanced fish feeds from local raw materials that can compete with imported feeds. The study aims to promote the development of the aquaculture industry by utilizing local resources and to ensure sustainable food security, thereby reducing dependency on imports..*

Today, in order to improve fish feed for aquaculture, it is necessary to carry out the following research and activities: studying the chemical composition of fish feed and identifying quantitative and qualitative deficiencies of feed components; investigating the proteins in feeds produced from local raw materials and finding ways to increase them; and examining and optimizing other components of fish feeds prepared from local raw materials.

To develop a principal technological scheme for producing fish feed from local raw materials and implement it in production; to prepare normative and technical documentation for the manufacture of compound feed for fish from local raw materials; to apply the production scheme of compound fish feed from local raw materials in practice; and to calculate the economic efficiency of the developed process. In the markets of our country, there are two main types of compound fish feeds: pelleted and extruded. Pelleted feeds are produced by mixing ingredients together with binders and then forming the mixture into granules. Extruded feeds, on the other hand, are prepared under high temperature and pressure, a process that alters the physical and chemical properties of the ingredients, thereby improving the quality of the resulting feed.

Extruded feed particles are more durable than pelleted ones, reducing breakage and the proportion of fine particles by at least 1%. In contrast, pelleted feeds may increase these indicators by 5–8%, and in some cases, up to 10%. The use of extruded feeds in fish feeding reduces the amount of feed dust entering the water by 75%, which helps to decrease the pollution of water bodies.

The main objectives of this processing encompass three key directions:

improving carbohydrate digestibility: the hydrolysis of starch converts it into simpler compounds such as dextrins and sugars. This process is particularly important for juvenile fish, as their enzymatic systems are not sufficiently developed to efficiently digest starch;

inactivation of inhibitors and antinutritional factors: this process eliminates substances that interfere with nutrient digestion, thereby enhancing overall digestive efficiency. *ashyoni sterilizastiya qilish: qayta ishlash, mikroflora darajasini pasaytirishga yordam beradi va bu mikroblarning ifloslanishini oldini olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.*

First, the raw materials are received and cleaned, followed by dosing, grinding, and mixing processes. The biomass is then moistened, heated, and disinfected in a conditioner, which improves its plasticity and formability prior to extrusion. Subsequently, the raw material is fed into the extruder, where it is compressed and forced under pressure through a die (forming plate). This plate contains openings with various shaping elements. As a result, the product exits in the form of a continuous strand and is cut into granules by rapidly rotating knives.

Within the production line, feed raw materials are processed under high temperature and pressure, ensuring complete thermal treatment and sterilization of the final product. The equipment enables control of the expansion degree of feed pellets in water by regulating material moisture content, composition, heating temperature, and the residence time in the extruder.

The fish feed production line is capable of producing both sinking and floating feeds. Different feed characteristics are achieved through the application of various processing procedures and types of equipment. The production line consists of the following stages: raw material mixing, pre-treatment, extrusion, cooling, drying with oil spraying, polishing, and storage. (1-pic).

1-pic. Fish Feed Production Technological Line.

The fish feed production line produces pellets of various sizes and shapes, which allows the equipment to be adapted for the manufacture of a wide range of products.

2-pic. Product Samples.

The production of compound feed is of significant importance for fish cultivated in water bodies. Priority should be given to species such as trout, salmon, and char, which require rapid growth. The feed mixture should contain specific nutrients and energy sources that facilitate a quick increase in fish weight and size. Additionally, this approach to compound feeding can also be effective for crustaceans and eel species..

References:

1. Батракова Ю. М., Даниленко И. Ю., Японцев А. Э., Лебедев С. Ю. Разработка и эффективность использования комбикормов для ценных пород рыб / Аграрная наука и инновационное развитие животноводства - основа экологической безопасности продовольствия: Национальная научно - практическая конференция: сборник статей, Саратов, 25-26 мая 2021 года. - Саратов: ООО "Центр социальных агроинноваций СГАУ", 2021. - С. 3-6.
2. Ранделин А. В., Батракова Ю. М., Даниленко И. Ю., Японцев А. Э. Использование низкочастотных комбикормов в кормлении ценных пород рыб / Инновационные технологии в агропромышленном комплексе в современных экономических условиях: Материалы Международной научно - практической конференции, Волгоград, 10-12 февраля 2021 года. - Волгоград: Волгоградский государственный аграрный университет, 2021. - С. 351-355.
3. Саттаров К.К., Хазраткулов Ж.З., Султонова Х.Х. Балиқлар учун озуқа қўшимчаларни ривожлантиришда инновацион ёндашилиши. "Кимё, органик моддалар ва нефт- газ сохалардаги долзарб муаммолар ва инновацион ечимлар" мавзусидаги Республика илмий амалий анжуман Материаллар тўплами. (14-15 ноябр. 2024) Наманган. 517-518 б
4. Хазраткулов Ж.З., Саттаров К.К. Использование белковой муки в комбикормах для рыб. Техника и технология пищевых производств. Тезисы докладов XIII Международной научной конференции студентов и аспирантов. Могилев. 2024. С. 69.
5. Саттаров, К. К., & Хазраткулов, Ж. З. Ў. (2025). СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ПРОТЕИНА В КОРМАХ ДЛЯ РЫБ. *Universum: технические науки*, 5(10 (139)), 20-22.